

Gender Differences in Motivation and its Influence on Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement in Mathematics in Rivers State.

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Abstract

This study investigated gender differences in motivation and their influence on senior secondary school students' achievement in mathematics. The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. A sample of one hundred sixty-seven (167) senior secondary school two (2) students, made up of 96 females and 71 males, from four (4) co-educational secondary schools in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria was used. An FB-Mathematics Achievement Test (FB-MAT) and a 4-point Likert scale Motivation Inventory (MI) with sections on self-efficacy and task value, were used as instruments for data collection. The data obtained were analyzed using t-tests and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC). Findings from the two instruments, the Motivation Inventory and FB-MAT found that male and female students performed at similar levels in mathematics; however, motivational factors in terms of self-efficacy and task value showed notable gender-based variations in favour of the male students. It recommends, among others, that both pre-service and in-service teachers be trained and retrained on how to recognize and address various forms of gender bias and stereotype reduction. Likewise, teachers should adopt inclusive classroom cultures that build self-efficacy in female students and emphasize learning goals for all.

Keywords: Gender differences, mathematics motivation, academic achievement, self-efficacy, task value.

Introduction

The senior secondary school level is a critical stage in students' academic careers because foundational knowledge is expanded and related to complex problem-solving scenarios. This level of education, as described in the Nigeria National Policy on Education (2013) aims at laying the foundation for lifelong learning, careers, and human development. In the National Economic and Empowerment Development Strategy (NEEDS), Vision 20: 2020 and the Transformation Agenda, it is also described as the post-basic level of education, a link between the basic and tertiary levels, with the objective of preparing learners for useful living within society and for the pursuit of tertiary education for those willing and able to withstand it. It is at this stage that career goals and educational pathways are defined. Mathematics at this level serves as both an academic requirement and a gateway to competitive tertiary education opportunities. Students' motivation and experiences in mathematics during secondary school shape their future academic and professional choices. Within the school curriculum, mathematics is made a core subject because it holds a pivotal place due to its importance. Learners' logical reasoning, analytical thinking, and problem-solving abilities are formed and strengthened at this level (Boaler, 2016). Mathematics serves as a foundational subject for academic progression and career readiness, particularly in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. There are hardly any aspects, fields, occupations, or

profession that mathematical concepts and principles are not applied. Its application extends beyond classroom instruction, influencing everyday activities such as managing finances and driving technological advancements (Forgasz & Leder, 2017). The concepts of ratio and proportion are applied in food preparation, production of chemicals for pest and weed control. Despite the universal importance of mathematics, it remains one of the most challenging and polarizing subjects among students, as students' achievement in mathematics, both in internal and external examinations, has not been encouraging. According to Brown et al. (2008), some students exhibited strong interest, aptitude, found personal fulfillment, and excelled in mathematical pursuits, while others struggled with low motivation, anxiety, low confidence, and disengagement. Else-Quest et al. (2010) reported that these factors often lead to poor academic achievement, uneven representation in mathematics courses, and gaps in mathematics achievement, especially among students of different genders. Understanding the psychological and sociocultural factors, such as gendered differences in motivation, self-belief, and subject valuation, will aid in identifying the root causes of poor achievement.

Motivation is the process that initiates, directs, and sustains goal-oriented behavior; it is a psychological trait with various aspects, such as self-efficacy, task value, interest, and beliefs about one's abilities. All of these affect learners' approaches to learning. Pintrich and De Groot (1990) opined that motivation is a critical determinant of students' academic engagement and achievement; it affects how students perceive tasks, regulate learning, and respond to challenges. Motivated students are more likely to engage actively in problem-solving, invest effort, seek help when needed, persist through difficulties, and utilize effective learning strategies. Conversely, students who lack motivation may avoid academic tasks, procrastinate, or attribute failure to internal deficiencies (Wigfield & Cambria, 2010). In mathematics, motivation patterns are strong because the subject often requires high cognitive demand, abstract reasoning, exacerbate student anxiety, sustained effort, and strategic thinking. Motivation is often influenced by learners' previous academic experiences and perceived success or failure. In the Expectancy-Value Theory developed by Atkinson (1964) and further used within educational psychology by Eccles (1984) and Wigfield (2000), posits that motivation to perform a task arises from an individual's belief in their ability to succeed (expectancy) and the personal importance or attractiveness of the task. Task value is a key construct that pertains to the perceived importance, usefulness, and interest of a task. It is influenced by cultural, societal, and familial messages about the usefulness and relevance of mathematics. Motivation comprises four components, namely attainment value, which reflects the personal significance of excelling at a task; intrinsic value, refers to the enjoyment derived from engaging in the activity while utility value, which captures the extent to which the task supports current or future aspirations; and cost value, which involves the sacrifices in time and opportunity associated with completing it (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002).

Self-efficacy in Bandura (1997) Social Cognitive Theory refers to the belief individuals have in their capability to perform specific tasks successfully. It influences students' willingness to take on challenging tasks, persist in the face of difficulties presented by the task, and approach problem-solving. Moses (2024) reported that high self-efficacy correlates with greater resilience, more effective learning strategies, and higher achievement. Students with strong self-efficacy in mathematics are more likely to attribute success to internal factors such as effort and strategy use, while those with low self-efficacy may attribute failure to a lack of ability, which gives rise to poor attempts and attendance in mathematics lessons and poor achievement. Zekpe and Leach (2010) stated that motivation and student dispositions influence learners' ability to engage in interactive

learning. Students who believe they can succeed in mathematics are more likely to find the subject meaningful and worth pursuing. Conversely, students who see no value in mathematics may not bother to build their competence. Self-efficacy and task value affect students' achievement and career choices.

Traditionally, mathematics has been stereotypically associated with males competence, leading to a phenomenon known as “stereotype threat,” The male receive more encouragement, which boosts their perceived competence to pursue mathematics and STEM-related careers. On the other hand, stereotype threat undermines female students' confidence and reduces their motivation, even in the presence of comparable ability to that of their male peers. Studies have shown that boys often report higher self-efficacy in mathematics than girls, even when achievement levels are similar. Huang (2013) reported that male students exhibited higher self-efficacy in mathematics than females in a meta-analysis study; also, Kasturi et al. (2021) carried out a study on 226 middle school students to determine differences in self-efficacy and it revealed that the self-efficacy of male students was a little higher than that of females. This shows that self-confidence in male students often leads to higher participation and perseverance, whereas some female students may avoid challenging courses or underestimate their ability, thereby limiting their academic and career trajectories. Similarly, gender differences in task value are evident, with boys typically perceiving greater utility and interest in mathematics. Girls, in contrast, may view the subject as less aligned with their future goals, particularly if they do not see female role models in mathematics-related fields.

By examining the relationships among gender, motivation, and achievement, educators can better support learners and promote more equitable outcomes in mathematics education. Encouraging equitable participation in mathematics requires creating learning environments that challenge gender stereotypes, foster positive motivational beliefs, and promote inclusive teaching practices. Hence, this study sought to investigate how self-efficacy and task value differ across genders and how these differences affect achievements.

Purpose of the study

The aim of the study is to examine how male and female students differ in their motivation toward mathematics. Specifically;

1. To determine the mean difference between male and female students' achievement in mathematics.
2. To determine the mean difference between male and female motivation in mathematics.
3. To determine the relationship between the components of mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement.

Research Questions:

1. What is the mean difference in the male and female achievement scores in mathematics?
2. What is the mean difference in the components of motivation between male and female students in mathematics?
3. What is the relationship between the components of mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement?

Hypothesis:

- H₁: There is no significant difference between male and female students' achievement in mathematics.
- H₂: There is no significant difference between male and female students' motivation in mathematics.

H₃: There is no significant relationship between mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement.

Methods

A purposive sampling technique was used to select Obio-Akpor Local Government Area (LGA) in Rivers State, while a random sampling technique was used to select four (4) coeducational public schools from the study area. All the students in Arm “A” of the SS2 class in the selected secondary schools were used as an intact class for the study, giving a total of 167 students (96 females and 71 males). Two instruments, namely the Motivation Inventory (MI), a 4-point Likert scale with three sections: Section A contains the bio-data, Section B: 10 items on self-efficacy, and Section C another 10 items on task value. The second instrument is the FB-Mathematics Achievement Test (FB-MAT) developed to measure actual mathematics achievement for comparison with motivation. It consists of 20-item multiple-choice questions with three distractors and one correct option. The drafted FB-MAT was validated by two lecturers at the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, one lecturer at Rivers State University, and two mathematics teachers from the four selected secondary schools in the study area. Items in FB-MAT were cleared and relevant with minor rewording. The changes were made and administered to a pilot sample of thirty (30) students who were not part of the study sample. After the tests were administered and scores obtained, a post-hoc analysis was carried out to evaluate the test's effectiveness and item difficulty analysis of the individual items in FB-MAT as suggested by Boopathiraj and Chellamani (2013). The difficulty index of FB-MAT range is 0.32 -0.40, while the reliability coefficient of FB-MAT was 0.75 using Kuder-Richardson formula 20(KR-20). Cronbach’s Alpha, designed to measure internal consistency in multi-item sub-scales, was used on the MI, and a reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained.

Method of Data Collection.

Approval was obtained from the principals of the selected schools to use the A arm of the SS2 classes. The researcher also met with the mathematics teachers of the selected classes for a briefing on the purpose and procedures of the research. With the help of these trained mathematics teachers, who served as research assistants, the MI and FB-MAT were administered to the students, and debrief sessions about confusing items were conducted with the students.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-tests, Cohen’s d, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation were used to test the hypothesis.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference in the male and female achievement scores in mathematics?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students

Gender	N	Mean Score	Achievement	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean Difference
Male	71	60.77		15.09	
Female	96	58.42		13.79	2.35

Table 1. showed that the male students had a mean score of 60.77 and SD of 15.09 in the achievement test, while the female students had a mean achievement score of 58.42 and an SD of 13.79. A mean difference of 2.35 was observed, though very minimal, but in favour of the male

students. This revealed that the gap is small, hence indicating a very minimal gender disparity in mathematics achievement.

Research Question 2: What is the mean difference in the components of motivation between male and female students in mathematics?

Table 2: Mean motivation (self-efficacy and task value) scores and standard deviations of male and female students.

Variable	Mean(96female)	Mean (male)	SD(Female)	SD (male)	Mean difference
Self-Efficacy	2.32	3.23	0.47	0.50	0.91
Task Value	2.76	3.21	0.40	0.43	0.45

Table 2. showed that the female students had a mean self-efficacy score of 2.32, while the male students had a mean score of 3.23. The mean difference between the male and female students in self-efficacy score is 0.91 in favour of the males. Also, in task value, the female students scored 2.76 while the mean male task value is 3.21 revealing a task value mean difference of 0.45 also in favour of the male students. It therefore revealed that the males had a higher score than the females in their belief that they can perform well in mathematics, as well as in the value they place on mathematics.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between the components of mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement?

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) between components of mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement.

Relationship	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	Strength of the Relationship
Self-Efficacy Score vs. Math Score	0.732	Strong Positive Relationship
Task Value Score vs. Math Score	0.678	Positive Relationship

The result of PPMC showed a correlation coefficient of 0.732 between the students' self-efficacy in motivation and mathematics achievement. This revealed a strong positive relationship and can be interpreted as a higher belief in students' ability to do math resulting in higher mathematics scores. Likewise, in the task- value score and Math score, it showed a correlation of r.678 which revealed a positive relationship between the value of mathematics, in its usefulness, importance, and applicability, and math achievement. The Pearson correlation coefficient for task value of 0. 678, though slightly lower than that for self-efficacy, suggests that students' belief in themselves, appreciation, or perceived importance of mathematics did substantially predict achievement. Therefore, the components of motivation do affect student achievement in mathematics.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant mean difference between male and female students' achievement in mathematics.

Table 4: t-Test and Cohen’s d test on male and female student mathematics achievement.

Gender	N	Mean Achievement Score	Standard Deviation (SD)	t-value	df	t-crit	Cohen’s d	Interpretation
Male	71	60.77	15.09	1.87	165	0.054	0.29	No significant difference
Female	96	58.42	13.79					

In Table 4, the t-value (0.054) is a little higher than the conventional 0.05 for statistical significance. This implies that the difference in the means is not substantial and is not statistically significant. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the male and female student achievement in mathematics is accepted. The effect size (Cohen's d = 0.29) which measures the relationship, also suggests a small to moderate practical difference. Hence, there are no gender gaps in the both male and female students in mathematics.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between male and female students’ motivation in mathematics.

Table 5: T-test on male and female students' motivation (self-efficacy and task value) scores

Variable	Mean (Female)	Mean (Male)	t-statistic	p-value
Self-Efficacy	2.32	3.23	-2.32	0.91
Task Value	2.76	3.21	-0.15	0.45

In Table 5, the male students' mean score in self-efficacy is 3.23 which is reportedly higher compared to female students' mean of 2.32. While the independent samples t-test showed a significant difference in mathematics self-efficacy between genders, with a t-test statistic of -2.32, at a p-value of 0.022. This suggests that gender influences students’ confidence in their mathematics ability. Likewise, the t-test results for task value showed a significant difference between male and female students, with a t-test *statistic of* -0.15 and a p-value *of* 0.296. Female students' mean of 2.76 is reported as a lower task value compared to the male mean score of 3.21. This indicates that male students place more importance on the usefulness and worth of mathematics.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the components of mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) between components of mathematics motivation and mathematics achievement

Relationship	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	Strength of the Relationship
Self-Efficacy Score vs. Math Score	0.732	Strong Positive Relationship
Task Value Score vs. Math Score	0.678	Positive Relationship

Table 6 shows that there exists a strong positive relationship (Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) = 0.732) between self-efficacy and mathematics achievement. This suggests that an increase in students' belief to succeed in mathematics (self efficacy) will tend to bring about an increase in their mathematics achievement. Likewise, there is a positive relationship (Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) = 0.678) between task value and mathematics achievement. This indicates that as a student's perceived value or importance of mathematics tasks increases, their mathematics achievement also tends to increase. This revealed that both self-efficacy and task value are

positively correlated with achievement in mathematics. with self-efficacy showing a stronger positive correlation. Therefore, an increase in mathematics achievement can be achieved through strengthening learners' belief in their mathematical abilities and appreciation of the value of mathematics.

Discussions

In this study, the findings showed no gender gaps in mathematics achievement and that the motivational components (self -efficacy and task value) differ in favour of the male students.

Gender Differences in Achievement Outcomes

The findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference found in the average scores of male and female students in mathematics. While males recorded a slightly higher mean score ($M = 60.77$) compared to females ($M = 58.42$), the observed difference was not statistically significant ($p = .063$), and the effect size was small (Cohen's $d = 0.29$). This result suggests that gender, as a variable, may not be a reliable predictor of students' academic achievement in mathematics. This finding is consistent with several recent Nigerian studies that have reported a narrowing or absence of gender gaps in mathematics performance. Akomolafe and Ogunmakin (2020) reported no significant gender-based differences in mathematics achievement among students exposed to inquiry-based learning strategies in southwestern Nigeria. They noted that modern instructional approaches, when applied equitably, tend to neutralize traditional achievement gaps attributed to gender. In addition, Akpan et al. (2023) on the technology-enhanced learning utilization of Symbolab manipulatives in instruction and performance of students in quadratic graphs, stating that gender has no significant effect on achievement; therefore, they recommended the use of technology-enhanced tools in mathematics instruction. This current study's view is in support of the findings of the previous studies that achievement in mathematics is influenced more by instructional quality, student motivation, and school environment than by gender alone.

Gender Differences in Motivation

Although the current study found no significant achievement gap, it did reveal significant gender differences in mathematics motivation. A gender-based difference in students' components of motivation in mathematics, both in the self-efficacy and task value domains, was reported. Ezeudu et al. (2022) reported that male students generally expressed higher confidence in mathematics tasks, despite similar levels of achievement. Male students displayed higher confidence regardless of ability, potentially due to cultural narratives reinforcing mathematical aptitude as a masculine trait. ($p < .05$). The implication is that gender-based motivational disparities persist even when achievement outcomes converge, highlighting the need for gender-sensitive pedagogical practices that address not only achievement but also affective and motivational variables and the importance of fostering positive academic self-concepts among female students. Therefore, Eccles and Wigfield's (2002) expectancy-value theory, which suggests the use of varied strategies, such as confidence-building for boys and relevance-focused teaching for girls, should be adopted and incorporated. Therefore, this study contributes to the growing evidence that mathematics achievement is not inherently gender-biased and that equitable educational practices can eliminate achievement disparities. Stakeholders should continue to promote inclusive instructional strategies and challenge cultural stereotypes that may inhibit female students' confidence and participation in mathematics learning.

Components of motivation and mathematics achievement.

This current study found a strong positive correlation between self-efficacy as a component of motivation and achievement in mathematics. It supports the findings of Zakariya et al. (2020) that

there is a potential causal relationship between mathematics self-efficacy and approaches to learning first-year calculus course. That is, students with high mathematics self-efficacy adopt deep approaches to learning first-year calculus, while those with low mathematics self-efficacy adopt surface approaches to learning the course. Thus, mathematics self-efficacy influences students' processes and strategies with which they study mathematics.

In another study conducted by Yang et al., (2024) on the relationship between mathematics self-efficacy and mathematics achievement gaps among students in grades 4, 8, and 12 using data from the 2019 National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP). The analysis of the NAEP data revealed, among other things, that mathematics self-efficacy emerged as a robust predictor of students' mathematics achievement, exhibiting significant effect sizes for Grades 4, 8, and 12. Furthermore, when students' mathematics self-efficacy was held constant, the mathematics achievement gaps among different student subgroups by gender, race/ethnicity, ELL, IEP, NSLP status narrowed, highlighting the importance of self-efficacy in addressing these disparities. It therefore emphasized the critical role of mathematics self-efficacy in influencing mathematics achievement gaps among students. Hence, it is recommended that policymakers and educators create intentional programs to reinforce students' self-efficacy in mathematics, ultimately ensuring fair educational opportunities and nurturing a more inclusive and impactful mathematics education system.

Results from this study showed that task value influences achievement in mathematics. This finding is consistent with Hemin et al. (2010) study on the role of self- efficacy, task value, and achievement goals in predicting learning approaches and mathematics achievement. One of the results from path analysis was the direct influence of task value on mastery goals and a deep learning approach. It indicated that students with high perceptions of task value in mathematics tended to choose mastery goals, and in the meantime, had a deeper learning approach, the result being more academic achievement among these students. This is a finding congruent with results from Ncororo et al (2022) on task value as a predictor of academic achievement among Form Three students in Meru County, Kenya. It is reported that task value causes achievement behavior among learners, leading to success. The Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient showed evidence of significant positive relationship between task value and academic achievement ($r(813) = .61, p < .05$). Regression analysis showed that task value accounted for 37% ($R^2 = .37, p < .05$) of the variations in academic achievement. Tasks' value stimulates students to enhance their competencies in mathematics. Once mathematics is recognized as useful for future goals, it is going to be perceived as more important regarding the fact that it is given value as a means to attaining goals.

Conclusion

Gender differences in mathematics motivation are nuanced and multidimensional. While achievement gaps may be closing, motivational disparities persist and have significant implications for equity in mathematics education. Addressing these differences requires intentional, evidence-informed practices that support all students' confidence, interest, and long-term engagement in mathematics. Based on the findings of the study, both self-efficacy and task value (the components of mathematics motivation) demonstrate a strong linear relationship with mathematics achievement. This study shows that motivation plays a connecting role between gender and achievement, indicating that any intervention should consider both students' beliefs and the surrounding structural factors.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers are encouraged to provide avenues for students to build self-efficacy and achieve success by guiding their learning with supportive steps and practical feedback.
2. Students should be given tasks that are not too difficult at first so they will not lead to decreased levels of success and motivation.
3. Retraining of teachers for professional development on how to recognize and address subtle forms of gender bias and stereotype reinforcement.
4. The government and curriculum planners should include real-life and socially relevant content in mathematics to increase the task value of mathematics, especially for female students.

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